

Split Happens: Combating Advanced Threats with Split Learning and Function Secret Sharing

1st Tanveer khan
Department of Computing Sciences
Tampere University
Tampere, Finland
tanveer.khan@tuni.fi

2nd Mindaugas Budzys
Department of Computing Sciences
Tampere University
Tampere, Finland
mindaugas.budzys@tuni.fi

3rd Antonis Michalas
Department of Computing Sciences
Tampere University
Tampere, Finland
antonios.michalas@tuni.fi

Abstract—Split Learning (SL) – splits a model into two distinct parts to help protect client data while enhancing Machine Learning (ML) processes. Though promising, SL has proven vulnerable to different attacks, thus raising concerns about how effective it may be in terms of data privacy. Recent works have shown promising results for securing SL through the use of a novel paradigm, named Function Secret Sharing (FSS), in which servers obtain shares of a function they compute and operate on a public input hidden with a random mask. However, these works fall short in addressing the rising number of attacks which exist on SL. In *SplitHappens*, we expand the combination of FSS and SL to U-shaped SL. Similarly to other works, we are able to make use of the benefits of SL by reducing the communication and computational costs of FSS. However, a U-shaped SL provides a higher security guarantee than previous works, allowing a client to keep the labels of the training data secret, without having to share them with the server. Through this, we are able to generalize the security analysis of previous works and expand it to different attack vectors, such as modern model inversion attacks as well as label inference attacks. We tested our approach for two different convolutional neural networks on different datasets. These experiments show the effectiveness of our approach in reducing the training time as well as the communication costs when compared to simply using FSS while matching prior accuracy.

Index Terms—Function Secret Sharing, Machine Learning, Privacy, Split Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The most widely used techniques for Privacy-preserving Machine Learning (PPML) are cryptographic techniques, such as Homomorphic Encryption (HE) [1]–[9] and Multi-Party Computation (MPC) [10]–[12]. HE allows users to perform mathematical computations, such as addition or multiplication, on encrypted data, while MPC aims to create methods that enable different parties to jointly compute a function on their private data, hence preserving privacy. Both techniques have been shown to improve the privacy of sensitive data while retaining high model accuracy [1], [13]. However, privacy comes at a cost and these techniques pertain to considerable computation and communication costs, that render their implementation in real-world scenarios difficult [14]. Consequently, researchers have been working to improve these techniques by introducing novel, cost-reducing approaches. One of these

solutions is the use of Function Secret Sharing (FSS) [15]. Through the use of FSS multiple parties can perform computations on a public input using a private, secretly shared function without identifying the data or the function itself. This approach greatly reduces communication costs when compared to traditional MPC techniques, such as Additive Secret Sharing or Garbled Circuits [11], [13], [16]. Despite these improvements, the costs of performing full FSS training remain impractical.

Because of high costs, there have been recent strides in the application of Split Learning (SL). This collaborative learning method has been applied to cryptographic techniques to both reduce the computational and communication costs of cryptographic techniques and address the privacy leakages inherently prevalent in SL [17]. Researchers have shown that using SL and HE can address the privacy issue of SL [14]. However, the main bottleneck is the high computational cost due to HE. To overcome this issue, many researchers use FSS instead of HE. *Make Split not Hijack (MSnH)* [18] was the first to combine FSS with Vanilla SL, significantly reducing computational costs compared to [14]. Another limitation of [14] is that the classification layer is executed on the server-side, inadvertently disclosing the model’s final prediction.

Consequently, we aimed at applying a U-shaped SL to FSS, for three reasons: (i) This type of SL is more favorable as it allows protection for both data and labels (ii) Launching an attack in this setting is more challenging because the available resources for the adversary present a variety of limitations compared to vanilla SL protocol (iii) Additionally, using SL with FSS, we enhance the security of SL, by reducing the privacy leakages caused by modern SL attacks, such as Pseudo-Client ATtack (PCAT) [19], Feature-Oriented Reconstruction Attack (FORA) [20], and Feature Sniffer [21] and generalize the security for any Model Inversion Attacks (MIA) and Label Inference Attacks (LIA).

Contributions. The main contributions of this work are:

- 1) We designed *SplitHappens* – an efficient PPML protocol using SL and FSS. *SplitHappens* reduces the computation [14] and communication costs of FSS [11], while enhancing the privacy of SL [18].
- 2) We have conducted experiments on three distinct datasets, namely MNIST, CIFAR and FMNIST, alongside two

models. Initially, we present the privacy leakage stemming from the use of SL. Subsequently, we explain how the identified privacy concern in SL is mitigated through the use of FSS. Additionally, we demonstrate that `SplitHappens` provides a more efficient alternative to the computationally expensive HE method discussed in prior work by Nguyen *et al.* [14]. Our approach enables running multiple layers on the server-side, unlike [14], which only considers one server-side layer.

- 3) Our findings demonstrated that our approach exhibits comparable performance in terms of communication cost and complexity, while maintaining the same level of accuracy to MSnH through all tests while providing increased security.
- 4) We expand security analysis of previous works, proving that `SplitHappens` can negate PCAT, FORA and Feature Sniffer, and its security can be generalized to other MIAs and LIAs.

II. RELATED WORK

Applying FSS in PPML has quickly become an active research field with a plethora of published works. `AriaNN` [11] is the first work that makes use of FSS for secure NN training and inference against a semi-honest adversary in a 2PC setting. `AriaNN` reports greatly reduced inference communication costs and inference time compared to other PPML MPC approaches, such as `ABY3` [22] and `SecureNN` [10], only having higher communication costs than `Falcon` [12] but lower computational complexity in the WAN setting. `Pika` [13] introduces a 3PC PPML solution against either a semi-honest or a malicious adversary. The work shows lower communication costs than previous MPC works (i.e. `ABY3`, `Falcon`), but has higher computation time than `Falcon` on higher batch sizes. Another recent FSS work is `LLAMA` [23], which implements a low-latency library for computing non-linear mathematical functions, useful to PPML, such as sigmoid, tanh, reciprocal square root, using FSS primitives. `Orca` [16] makes use of and expands the library proposed in `LLAMA` [23] to perform secure training and inference on NN architectures with GPU acceleration. `FssNN` [24] proposes a two-party FSS framework for secure NN training and makes improvements to various aspects in prior arts. All of these works show much better performance in terms of training and inference time as well as lower communication costs when compared to previous arts in MPC. This shows that FSS can greatly improve current work in PPML. However, communication costs and computational complexity are still greatly increased comparing to plaintext alternatives. As a result, combining these works with other techniques, such as SL, could provide a substantial improvement to lowering said costs for NN training.

SL provides significant advantages in terms of splitting the computational cost of training NNs for a user by outsourcing a part of the training process to a server. Initially, it was believed as a promising approach in terms of client raw data protection, as parties exclusively share activation maps (ATm) between them. However, a potential vulnerability arises during end-to-

end training, where the exchange of gradients at the cut layer could inadvertently encode private features or labels, posing a risk to data privacy. Abuadbbba *et al.* [17] proposed using SL when training and classifying 1-dimensional data on CNN models. They identified that SL achieves comparable accuracy to centralized models, but noted that SL by itself has multiple privacy leakages hampering the confidentiality of the input data. Moreover, researchers have found that SL is susceptible to Feature Space Hijacking Attack (FSHA) [25], LIA [21], MIA [19], [20], [26] and Visual Invertibility (VI) [17].

The leakages highlight the importance of addressing data privacy concerns when implementing SL techniques. As such, researchers have attempted combining different Privacy-preserving Techniques (PPTs) with SL to address these attacks. For example, Abuadbbba *et al.* [17] tried two privacy mitigation techniques—adding more hidden layers on the client-side and using Differential Privacy (DP). However, both these techniques suffer from a loss of model accuracy, particularly when DP is used. Some other works like `Split Ways` [27] or `Split` without a Leak [14] make use of HE to encrypt the ATm of SL before outsourcing them to the server. This way, the model retains equivalent accuracy when compared to plaintext SL, and addresses some of the privacy leakages known in SL.

In all of the covered FSS works, the researchers employ FSS on the entire model, which in turn increases computational complexity and communication overhead. To the best of our knowledge, only one work combines SL with FSS in the literature [18]. However, it has a limitation: the server can access labels and model output, compromising user data privacy. Our approach improves privacy in ML applications, solve the privacy leakage caused by SL and reduce both the communication and computation costs of FSS.

III. PRELIMINARIES

Split Learning: SL is a collaborative learning technique [28] in which an ML model is split into two parts. The client part (f_{θ_C}), comprises the first few layers ($1, \dots, l$) of the model, with l being the last layer on the client-side. The server part (f_{θ_P}), encompasses the remaining layers of the model ($l + 1, \dots, L$), with L being the last layer on the server-side. The client and server collaborate to train the split model without having access to each other’s parts.

The aim of SL is to protect client privacy by allowing clients to train part of the model, and share ATm (instead of raw data) with a server running the remaining part of the model. It is also utilized to reduce the client’s computational overhead by merely running a few layers rather than the entire model. In the local model, there is no split, while in the vanilla SL there is a split with labels being shared with the server. In contrast, the U-shaped SL model also has a split though the final layer is executed on the client-side, resulting in no sharing of labels with the server. Initially, it was believed that SL is a promising approach in terms of client raw data protection, as parties exclusively share ATm between them. However, studies have shown the possibility of privacy leakage in SL [17], [29].

Fig. 1: SplitHappens: Private U-shaped SL

Function Secret Sharing: FSS provides a way for additively secret-sharing a function f from a given function family F . A two-party FSS scheme splits a function $f : (0, 1)^n \rightarrow G$, for some abelian group G , into functions described by keys such that $f = f_0 + f_1$ and every strict subset of the keys hides f . Formally an FSS scheme can be defined as [15]:

Definition 1 (Function Secret Sharing). *Let FSS be a 2-party Function Secret Sharing scheme, that for some class F has a pair of Probabilistic Polynomial-Time (PPT) algorithms $\text{FSS} = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{EvalAll})$ such that:*

- $(f_0, f_1) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda, f)$: The KeyGen algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm that takes as input the security parameter λ and some function f and outputs two different function shares (f_0, f_1) (also called function keys).
- $\text{EvalAll}(j, f_j, x_{pub}) \rightarrow f_j(x_{pub})$: The EvalAll algorithm is a deterministic algorithm that takes three parameters, the input bit $j \in \{0, 1\}$, the function key f_j , and the public data x_{pub} and outputs the shares $f_j(x_{pub})$.

An FSS scheme should satisfy the following two properties:

- **Secrecy:** A single key (f_j) hides the original function f .
- **Correctness:** Adding the local shares gets the same output as the original function:

$$\Pr[f_0 + f_1 = f | (f_0, f_1) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda, f)] = 1 \quad (1)$$

IV. FSS BASED U-SHAPED SL PROTOCOL

This section presents the SplitHappens protocol’s training algorithms and system model.

A. Actors in the model

- **Client:** The client provides the training data and is capable of computing the initial layer of the model in plaintext. The client uses their private data to compute the initial layers and shares ATm and the remaining layers with the servers. In our setup, the client also computes the final prediction of the model *independently* and does not share the truth labels to the server.
- **Servers:** Our protocol requires two servers to perform computations on the secret shares. Based on the received x_{pub} , each server makes computations on the underlying ML model. Since we employ the U-shaped SL protocol,

the servers are unable to compute the model’s final output as the servers do not receive the truth labels. In our approach, the final output of the model is computed on the client-side. We operate under the assumption that there is no collusion between the two servers and that the servers are hosted independently to avoid reconstructing the original data from the shares. This assumption is realistic and consistent with other 2PC works [11], [30].

B. Training the SplitHappens protocol

We have used algorithm 1 and algorithm 2 to train SplitHappens. It consists of:

Initialization phase. The initialization phase occurs only once, whereas the other phases continue until the model iterates through all epochs. This phase consists of socket and random weight initialization Φ . The client establishes a socket connection and synchronizes the hyperparameters η, n, N, E . ATm and the gradient are initially set to zero \emptyset . These parameters must be synchronized on both sides to be trained in the same way. In SplitHappens, the client executes the first few layers as well as the last layer of the model, while the remaining layers are executed on the server-side.

Forward propagation. In algorithm 1, the client carries out forward propagation on the input x using f_{θ_C} to calculate ATm . To prevent client data privacy, the private input (ATm) is first masked using random mask α to construct the public input x_{pub} before sending it to the server. Once x_{pub} is constructed, the next step is to send x_{pub} to the server. Once x_{pub} is computed, the client sends it to the servers to continue the forward propagation. As can be seen in Figure 2, we have two servers labeled as P_0 and P_1 . Each server receives the public input x_{pub} and initiates forward propagation by executing their respective portion of the model. On the server-side, we employ FSS, to compute the function keys. Specifically, these keys are generated for the ReLU layers. We employ the FSS KeyGen algorithm, to create these keys for each server. Additionally, to compute the FC layers on the server-side, we used beaver triples. As depicted in algorithm 2, each server executes their share of the layer on x_{pub} until the $L - 1^{th}$ layers. After executing the $L - 1^{th}$ layer, each server sends the output to the client. Upon reception, the client processes the final output layer to get the predicted output \hat{y} . The next step involves calculating the loss, and this is computed using the equation $J \leftarrow \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}_j, y_j)$. In U-shaped SL, the loss calculation involves multiple steps. *First, the model’s output is represented in fixed precision. This output represents the actual values without any secret sharing, as it remains on the client-side. Next, the target values are encrypted into additive shares. These encrypted shares are then used to compute the loss function, which also remains in the form of additive shares. These loss shares are sent back to the servers for further computation.*

The model’s privacy is preserved by using additive shares for both the target values and the loss. The target values remain encrypted and distributed across the servers, ensuring that no individual server can access the original target values. Simi-

TABLE I: Parameters and description in the algorithms

#	ML Parameters	Description	FSS Parameters	Description
1	\mathbf{D}, m	Dataset, Number of data samples	s_j	Random Seed
2	x, y	Input data samples, Ground-truth labels	α	Random mask
3	η, p	Learning rate, Momentum	P_0, P_1	Server 1 and 2
4	Δ	Backpropagation gradients	f_0, f_1	Function shares (function keys)
5	n, x_{pub}	Batch size, Public input	f_{θ_P}	Server-side model
6	N	Number of batches to be trained	f_{θ_C}	Client-side model
7	E	Number of training epochs	f, f^{-1}	Encoder, Decoder
8	f^i	Linear or non-linear operation of layer i	f_j^{FC}	FC part for server j
9	ATm^i	Output activation map of f^i	f_j^{ReLU}	ReLU FSS key for server j

Fig. 2: Utilizing function secret sharing between two servers for SplitHappens

larly, the loss remains encrypted throughout the computation, preventing any potential privacy leaks.

Backward propagation. After calculating the loss the client starts the backward propagation by computing $\frac{\partial J}{\partial \hat{y}_j}$ and $\frac{\partial J}{\partial ATm_j^{(L)}}$ using the chain rule and sends the values to the server. Upon reception the servers first compute $\frac{\partial J}{\partial ATm_j^{L-1}}$ and continue the backward propagation until layer $l+1$ (see algorithm 2). Both the servers update the weights (w) and biases (b) of their respective layers using $w = w - \eta \frac{\partial J}{\partial w}$ and $b = b - \eta \frac{\partial J}{\partial b}$. After updating w and b of the layer $l+1$, the server calculates $\frac{\partial J}{\partial ATm_j^{l+1}}$ and sends it to the client. Upon reception, the client calculates the gradient of J with respect to w and b of the layers residing on the client-side and updates w and b . The forward and backward propagation continue until the model converges to learn a suitable set of parameters.

V. THREAT MODEL & SECURITY ANALYSIS

Threat model: In SL, collaborative learning of local models introduces potential risk due to interactions among the participants [31]. In this study, we examine a scenario involving a semi-honest adversary, denoted as \mathcal{ADV} , capable of corrupting one of the two servers engaged in our protocol. In this context, the corrupted parties adhere to the protocol's specifications, all while attempting to gather as much information as possible

about the inputs and function shares of other participants. Within our specific framework, secure protocols are employed to facilitate collaborative CNN model training by three parties: a client and two servers. The client, who also serves as the data owner (note that considering a malicious client in this context is pointless), initiates the process by executing the initial layers of the model. This action produces an intermediary result, denoted as ATm , which is subsequently kept confidential through FSS between two independent servers. Following this, these two servers proceed to jointly train the remaining segments of the model using the client's data, achieved by employing the FSS protocol.

As such, behavior of \mathcal{ADV} can be summarized as:

- \mathcal{ADV} does not possess information about the participating clients, except necessary details required to execute the SL protocol.
- \mathcal{ADV} is familiar with a shadow dataset (\tilde{x}), from the same domain as the clients' training set x . In this case no element of \tilde{x} overlap with x , i.e. $\tilde{x} \cap x = \emptyset$.
- \mathcal{ADV} has no knowledge of the architecture and weights of the whole model. However, she can gather information and make assumptions of the client model and train an architecturally similar model f_{θ_C} using the \tilde{x} .

Attack 1 (Label Inference Attack). *Let \mathcal{ADV} represents an adversary acting as one of the servers. \mathcal{ADV} successfully*

Algorithm 1: Client-Side

```

1  soc ← socket initialized with port and address;
2  η, n, N, E ← soc.synchronize
3  {w(i), b(i)} ∀i∈{0..l} ← initialize using Φ
4  {ATm(i)} ∀i∈{0..l} ← ∅, {∂J/∂ATm(i)} ∀i∈{0..l} ← ∅
5  for e ∈ E do
6    for each batch (x, y) generated from D do
7      Forward propagation :
8      for i ← 1 to l do
9        | ATm(i) ← fθC(xpub(i))
10     end
11     xpubi ← ATm(i) + α
12     soc.send(xpubi)
13     soc.receive(ATmjL-1)
14     Compute(ATmL-1)
15     ŷ ← sL(ATm(L-1))
16     J ← ℒ(ŷ, yj)
17     Backward propagation :
18     Compute {∂J/∂ŷj} & ∂J/∂ATmj(L)}
19     soc.send(∂J/∂ATmj(L)}, ∂J/∂wj(L)})
20     soc.receive(∂J/∂ATmj(l+1))
21     Compute {∂J/∂ATml}
22     for i ← l to 1 do
23       | Compute {∂J/∂w(i)}, ∂J/∂b(i)} and Update w(i), b(i)
24     end
25   end
26 end

```

Algorithm 2: Server-Side

```

1  soc ← socket initialized with port and address;
2  η, n, N, E ← soc.synchronize
3  for e ∈ E do
4    for i ← l + 1 to L - 1 do
5      Forward propagation :
6      soc.receive(xpubi)
7      for j = 0, 1 do
8        | ATmjL-1 ← fθPj(xpub)
9      end
10     soc.send(ATmjL-1)
11     Backward propagation :
12     soc.receive(∂J/∂ATmj(L)}, ∂J/∂wj(L)})
13     for j = 0, 1 do
14       | Compute {∂J/∂ATmjL-1}
15       for i ← L - 1 to l + 1 do
16         | Compute {∂J/∂w(i)}, ∂J/∂b(i)} and Update w(i), b(i)
17       end
18       soc.send(∂J/∂ATmj(l+1))
19     end
20   end
21 end

```

performs a LIA if she manages to infer the private labels by exploiting the client's output layer; if the client computes only the output layer locally and shares it with the server, the private labels can be inferred.

Attack 2 (Model Inversion Attack). Let \mathcal{ADV} represents an adversary acting as one of the servers. \mathcal{ADV} successfully performs MIA if she manages to infer input samples using client's model output. \mathcal{ADV} use these inferred input samples to train a new model that is functionally similar to f_{θ_c} .

A. Security analysis

With our threat model established, we can now move forward to demonstrate the security of our protocol.

Proposition 1 (LIA Soundness). Let \mathcal{ADV} be a semi-honest adversary that corrupts at most one of the two servers (P_0 or P_1) involved in the protocol. Then \mathcal{ADV} cannot launch a successful Label Inference attack.

Proof. Let \mathcal{ADV} be a semi-honest adversary that has compromised P_0 or P_1 . In addition to that, assume \mathcal{ADV} gains access to: i) The public input $x_{pub} = ATm + \alpha$, ii) One part of $f_{\theta_{P_b}}$, where b is either 0 or 1, iii) An architecturally similar model \tilde{f}_{θ_C} to the client's model¹ f_{θ_C} that produces gradients $\tilde{\Delta}$, iv) The masked gradients $\Delta_{pub} = \Delta + \alpha$, where Δ is the back propagation gradients and α is a sufficiently large random mask generated in FSS. Then, if \mathcal{ADV} cannot train an architecturally similar model \tilde{f}_{θ_C} that can produce similar gradients to f_{θ_C} , our protocol is secure against LIA. Following our assumptions, let's assume two games.

Game 0: In this first game, both the challenger (\mathcal{CHAL}) and \mathcal{ADV} will generate their respective gradient values Δ and $\tilde{\Delta}$ from their models. \mathcal{CHAL} will then generate α and add it to Δ prior to sending Δ_{pub} back to \mathcal{ADV} . \mathcal{ADV} will then compare two values and choose the higher one. This game can be then simplified to a functionally similar game (**Game 1**).

Game 1: The core steps of the game are the same as in **Game 0**. In this case, instead of generating $\tilde{\Delta}$ and Δ from their respective models f_{θ_C} , \mathcal{ADV} and \mathcal{CHAL} will pick a random number x and x' between 0 and 1, respectively. Now assuming α is a sufficiently large random mask, which is much higher than x' , the resulting x'_{pub} will always be larger than x . And since \mathcal{ADV} cannot obtain the exact value of α applied to the generated number x' , due to this she will not be able to accurately compare x'_{pub} and x .

The same applies in **Game 0**, as \mathcal{ADV} will not be able to compare Δ_{pub} and $\tilde{\Delta}$, then \mathcal{ADV} will always assume that the gradients in Δ_{pub} point to the true label in every instance, as $\Delta_{pub} > \tilde{\Delta}$.

Thus, \tilde{f}_{θ_C} does not produce similar gradients to f_{θ_C} , ensuring our protocol is security against LIA. \square

Proposition 2 (MIA Soundness). Let \mathcal{ADV} be a semi-honest adversary that corrupts at most one of two servers (P_0 or P_1) involved in the protocol. Then \mathcal{ADV} cannot launch a successful MIA.

¹In an optimal case for LIA, the user has a single layer model, however, this is not a realistic assumption in all applications and we assume the clients model can contain an arbitrary number of layers, which can greatly reduce the accuracy of LIA [21].

Proof. Let \mathcal{ADV} be a semi-honest adversary that has compromised P_0 or P_1 . In addition to that, assume \mathcal{ADV} gains access to: (i) $x_{pub} = ATm + \alpha$ (ii) One part of $f_{\theta_{P_b}}$, where b is either 0 or 1, (iii) An architecturally similar model f_{θ_C} to the client’s model f_{θ_C} .

If \mathcal{ADV} cannot train an attack model that can reliably revert the ATm from x_{pub} back to its original form x , then our protocol is secure against MIA.

In MIA, \mathcal{ADV} attempts to use the output of f_{θ_C} to reconstruct raw input data, in this case \mathcal{ADV} relies on x_{pub} . Similarly, as in Proposition 1, the ATm produced by f_{θ_C} is not sent in plaintext, but is masked with a random mask α . Due to this, \mathcal{ADV} without knowing the random mask α , she would not be able to accurately make use of her attack model as it relies on an input similar to ATm , but receives x_{pub} . Assuming α is securely generated following the techniques used in FSS, then \mathcal{ADV} is unable to reliably revert the intermediate ATm from x_{pub} back to its original form x . Based on this we may conclude that our protocol is secure against MIA. \square

The security analysis we provide above as well as the proof against FSHA provided by the authors of MSnH [18] allows `SplitHappens` to be robust against a variety of different individual attacks. Attacks, such as PCAT [19] and FORA [20], rely on similar assumptions and steps as MIA or FSHA, as such it is possible to conclude that `SplitHappens` through the use of FSS and U-shaped SL is secure against these attack as well. This is due to the fact that `SplitHappens` never sends the smashed data directly to \mathcal{ADV} , as it is hidden with a pseudo-random mask α . This also applies to the gradients as `SplitHappens` never provide the \mathcal{ADV} with the gradients, but just a public input with the pseudo-random mask α (see Proposition 1 and Proposition 2).

GameExp $_{SplitHappens, \Delta}^{ind-fss-\alpha}$

<p>Game 0: \mathcal{ADV} computes: $f_{\theta_C} \rightarrow \Delta$</p> <p>$\mathcal{CHAL}$ computes: $f_{\theta_C} \rightarrow \Delta$ $\alpha \leftarrow \text{Rand}(\cdot)$ $\Delta_{pub} = \Delta + \alpha$ \mathcal{CHAL} sends Δ_{pub} to \mathcal{ADV}</p> <p>\mathcal{ADV} compares: Δ and Δ_{pub} and chooses higher one</p>	<p>Game 1: \mathcal{ADV} computes: $x \leftarrow \text{Rand}(\cdot)$</p> <p>$\mathcal{CHAL}$ computes: $x' \leftarrow \text{Rand}(\cdot)$; $\alpha \leftarrow \text{Rand}(\cdot)$, where $\alpha \gg x'$; $x'_{pub} = x' + \alpha$; \mathcal{CHAL} sends x'_{pub} to \mathcal{ADV}</p> <p>\mathcal{ADV} compares: x and x_{pub} and chooses higher one</p>
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VI. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Experimental setup: We test and compare our SL protocol with AriaNN [11] and MSnH [18]. To make this comparison, we first reproduced the results for the AriaNN implementation [11] and MSnH [18]. For the experiments, we used a machine running Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, processor 12th generation Intel Core i7-12700, 32 GB RAM mesa Intel graphics (ADL-S GT1). We implemented our code using Python 3.7 and is made available online² to support open and reproducible science.

²<https://github.com/UnoriginalOrig/SplitFSS>

FSS implemented using the PySyft framework³ and a modified version of AriaNN⁴. Communication costs are calculated by measuring the byte length of serialized objects sent through packets. Time measurements are taken by making use of the in-built Python `time` module. The loss is calculated using mean squared error. We provide the average of our experimental results in Table II. Also, we have selected two models for our experiments. **Network 1:** A 4-layered network with two Conv2D and two FC layers, utilizing Maxpool and ReLU function. **Network 2:** It contains two Conv2D and three FC layers, utilizing Maxpool and ReLU function.

A. Evaluation

This section provides outcomes derived from experiments.

The local models with and without SL are run in plaintext without making use of FSS to create a baseline to compare further results. They also measure the effects of FSS on the performance of the models. Since these models do not have FSS, they are represented as “Public” models. Second, we reproduce the results of AriaNN [11] and MSnH [18], which we use to compare them with the public models. Also, we compare our model `SplitHappens`, with the public U-shaped SL protocol. Then, we show the results of `SplitHappens` alongside those of AriaNN and MSnH. Since these protocols use FSS, they are presented as “Private”. *Plaintext models.* We compare the public vanilla and U-shaped SL protocols to the public local model. Our experiments indicate that training the vanilla and U-shaped SL protocols on plaintext data yields similar accuracy when compared to training the public local model as illustrated in Table II. The accuracy values align with those achieved by the public local model, suggesting that the SL model can be effectively applied to CNN models across all three datasets without experiencing a significant degradation in accuracy.

We also consider the training time and communication cost of the public vanilla and U-shaped SL model and compare it to the local model. The total training time for both network 1 and network 2 across all three models and datasets for 10 epochs is nearly identical, ranging between 1 and 2 minutes.

With regards to communication cost, we are considering costs on both the client and the server-side, as well as the total costs during training and testing. In Table II, we show the variation between the client-side and the server-side communication costs between the public local, vanilla and the U-shaped SL protocols. We observe that the public U-shaped SL approach has slightly higher server-side communication costs than the public vanilla and local model, but client-side communications for both vanilla and U-shaped SL are about $3 \times$ larger than the local model. This difference arises from the size of the data shared as in the local model, the client must send 28×28 images, while in the SL model, the client sends the ATm , which is only 8×8 .

In the Table II presented, it is noticeable that the U-shaped SL model has slightly higher total communication costs

³<https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft/tree/ryffel/0.2.x-fix-training>

⁴<https://github.com/LaRiffle/AriaNN>

(for both training and testing) compared to the vanilla SL models. This difference arises because, in the U-shaped SL model, there is more back-and-forth communication between the server and client involving ATm and gradients, resulting in relatively higher server-side communication costs when compared to the vanilla SL models. However, the client-side communication costs show only minor variations. Even though the vanilla and U-shaped SL model provides similar accuracy and has the same training and even better communication cost when compared to the locally computed model, it is essential to note that both these models introduce a privacy leakage, which we mitigate using FSS.

Comparison to other work We compare our work with AriaNN [11], which secures the entire model with FSS, and MSnH [18] where a hybrid approach combining SL and FSS was introduced. The results demonstrated that this approach addresses the privacy concern of SL while maintaining approximately the same accuracy as public local and vanilla SL models. Additionally, the authors claimed to achieve comparable accuracy to AriaNN in approximately 192 minutes, highlighting a significant advantage.

In our experimentation, we replicated the results for AriaNN and MSnH and compared them with our proposed approach `SplitHappens`. We tested all three models – AriaNN, MSnH, and `SplitHappens` – on their ability to train NN in a private manner. This end-to-end private training ensures that neither the model nor the gradients are ever accessible in plaintext. We report the training time and accuracy obtained by training (see Table II). While the accuracy might not match the best-known results due to the training setting, the procedure is consistent across all, ensuring a fair comparison. To thoroughly assess and compare the impact of FSS on performance, we initialized two models: one before applying FSS (referred to as “Public”) and one after applying FSS (referred to as “Private”) (see Table II), both with the same set of initial weights.

Comparison of private models with the public models: We compare each private model with its public counterpart: AriaNN with the public local model, MSnH with public vanilla SL, and `SplitHappens` with the public U-shaped SL protocol. This comparison helps us to determine whether using FSS impacts model accuracy. Subsequently, we compare our protocol, `SplitHappens`, with AriaNN and MSnH to evaluate its performance against SotA PPML protocols.

On MNIST dataset, for network 1, our analysis, clearly indicates that the accuracy obtained before and after applying FSS remains nearly identical. As can be seen in Table II, all private models have similar accuracy to their public counterparts with approximately a 2-3% loss in accuracy. Our proposed protocol, `SplitHappens`, follows this pattern, achieving a test accuracy of 97.21%, matching its public counterpart, the U-shaped SL protocol. For the case of network 2, there is a reduction in the accuracy of private models compared to their public counterparts. More specifically, each private models accuracy falls by approximately 10% when compared to their respective public model. Notably, `SplitHappens` had the best performance in this case from the private models.

For the CIFAR dataset, the accuracy of private models are lower than their public counterparts. Specifically, in network 1, AriaNN achieves an accuracy of 65.57%, MSnH achieves 45.46%, and `SplitHappens` achieves 45.78%, whereas the SL public models demonstrate superior performance with higher accuracies by 20%. Similarly, in network 2, private models also underperform relative to their public versions. This disparity indicates that private models experience a drop in accuracy on more complex datasets.

Naturally, in all benchmarks the private training time is higher than the public counterparts with increases upwards of $900\times$. Similarly, communication costs for private models were $2 - 3\times$ higher, than their public counterparts. This shows major differences in computational and communication overhead between the public and private models. The trade-off, in this case, is the improved security provided by using `SplitHappens` or other FSS-based works.

B. Experimental Results

To test the applicability of our approach, we used three datasets: (1) MNIST (2) CIFAR (3) FMNIST on two networks: (i) Network 1: A 4-layered network with two Conv2D and two FC layers, utilizing Maxpool and ReLU function. and (ii) Network 2: It contains two Conv2D and three FC layers, utilizing Maxpool and ReLU function.

In conclusion, FSS demonstrates its potential as a promising solution for maintaining data privacy while achieving commendable accuracy in ML. Nonetheless, it is important to remember that FSS comes with significant drawbacks in terms of the time it takes to train models and the extra communication needed. This should be carefully weighed when deciding if it is the right choice when selecting a privacy-preserving framework for specific use cases. Importantly, FSS solutions help reduce privacy leakages possible in the public models or in plaintext SL. The use of SL with FSS through `SplitHappens` or MSnH additionally reduces the high computational and communication overhead of training the model fully with FSS by quite a large margin.

Comparison of private models: In this section, we compare `SplitHappens` with AriaNN and MSnH. As shown in Table II, our approach achieves comparable accuracy to AriaNN and MSnH (except on CIFAR dataset) while significantly reducing training time. On the MNIST dataset, `SplitHappens` achieves a test accuracy of 97.21% on network 1 and 91.98% on network 2, which is comparable to the performance of both AriaNN and MSnH. Similarly, on the FMNIST dataset, `SplitHappens` attains accuracies of 79.23 on network 1 and 84.22 on network 2, closely align with the results of AriaNN and MSnH. However, on the CIFAR dataset, while `SplitHappens` accuracy is similar to that of MSnH, it is slightly lower than that achieved by AriaNN. These findings indicate that `SplitHappens` performs on par with existing protocols, demonstrating its effectiveness and efficiency.

In terms of total communication cost, `SplitHappens` exhibits slightly higher communication costs than MSnH but remains significantly lower than AriaNN. However, the

TABLE II: Training and testing results for various privacy-preserving models

PETs				Training Statistics				Testing Statistics	
Models	Datasets	FSS	SL	Client Comm (MB)	Server Comm (MB)	Training Time (min)	Training Comm (MB)	Testing Comm (MB)	Testing Accuracy (%)
Network 1	MNIST	Public	Local	1931.85	1.65	1.44	1933.51	313.39	99.36
			Vanilla	641.17	25.74	1.42	666.70	102.52	99.26
			U-shaped	641.17	51.49	1.44	692.44	106.79	99.30
		Private	AriaNN	3861.32	3.57	1190.59	3864.90	1253.01	97.01
			MSnH	1332.08	3.57	161.49	1335.66	204.85	97.09
			SplitHappens	1334.17	99.41	171.28	1433.59	205.12	97.21
	CIFAR	Public	Local	4740.91	1.43	1.21	4742.35	939.60	66.04
			Vanilla	555.58	1.43	1.20	556.53	102.53	66.37
			U-shaped	555.57	22.89	1.20	578.47	106.82	65.79
		Private	AriaNN	9479.76	2.97	2234.23	9483.29	3757.80	65.57
			MSnH	2130.56	2.97	450.02	2133.96	3757.79	45.46
			SplitHappens	2130.55	85.81	569.82	2216.80	3758.09	45.78
	FMNIST	Public	Local	1931.92	1.72	1.52	1933.65	313.40	89.88
			Vanilla	666.70	1.72	1.52	668.43	102.50	89.44
			U-Shaped	666.70	27.47	1.53	694.17	106.82	89.65
		Private	AriaNN	3860.53	3.57	1814.74	3864.76	1253.01	74.44
			MSnH	2556.67	3.57	354.50	2560.68	1253.01	77.29
			SplitHappens	2556.68	102.99	362.36	2660.10	1253.30	79.23
Network 2	MNIST	Public	Local	2507.00	1.72	1.05	2508.73	409.25	99.24
			Vanilla	1011.74	1.72	1.105	1013.47	160.04	95.68
			U-Shaped	1011.74	27.47	1.16	1039.21	164.33	99.15
		Private	AriaNN	5010.25	3.52	2581.12	5014.97	1636.40	89.30
			MSnH	3936.86	3.57	753.09	3941.39	1636.39	85.32
			SplitHappens	3936.87	102.99	514.08	4040.81	1636.69	91.98
	CIFAR	Public	Local	6178.61	1.43	0.91	6180.05	1227.14	64.65
			Vanilla	843.11	1.43	0.90	844.55	160.04	63.28
			U-Shaped	843.11	22.89	0.96	866.01	164.33	63.70
		Private	AriaNN	12354.02	2.97	3343.90	12358.08	4907.95	63.57
			MSnH	3280.71	2.97	843.55	3284.64	4907.95	44.24
			SplitHappens	3280.71	85.81	996.12	3367.48	4908.24	44.07
	FMNIST	Public	Local	2507.00	1.72	1.10	2508.73	409.25	89.57
			Vanilla	1011.74	1.72	1.12	1013.47	160.04	89.22
			U-Shaped	1011.74	27.47	1.20	1039.21	164.33	89.58
		Private	AriaNN	5009.68	3.57	2466.91	5014.25	1636.40	86.82
			MSnH	3937.15	3.57	498.64	3941.67	1636.39	77.92
			SplitHappens	3937.14	103.00	749.61	4041.10	1636.69	84.22

server-side communication cost for SplitHappens is higher compared to both MSnH and AriaNN. This is because, in SplitHappens, the output layer of the model is on the client-side, necessitating more communication between the client and server for sharing the ATm and gradients.

Another aspect to consider is that MSnH requires minimal preprocessing communication batch (0.119 MB), representing a substantial reduction compared to AriaNN (10.572 MB per batch). This efficiency is attributed to the execution of client-side layer in plaintext, as opposed to AriaNN, which

involves more interaction between the parties, increasing the communication cost. SplitHappens also demonstrates “efficiency” in preprocessing communication costs, which are even marginally better than those of MSnH due to few layers requiring FSS computation. Additionally, the client-side communication cost of SplitHappens is $2\times$ lower than AriaNN while remaining similar to that of MSnH. Furthermore, SplitHappens demonstrates greater efficiency compared to AriaNN with a training time shorter than that of AriaNN. SplitHappens operates nearly $3\times$ more efficiently than

AriaNN, reducing the overall training duration. The shorter training time is due to executing all client-side layers in plain, which avoids expensive techniques such as beaver triples and FSS. While `SplitHappens` exhibits a notable improvements over AriaNN, its training time is marginally longer than that of MSnH. This comparison highlights `SplitHappens`'s robust performance, striking a balance between efficiency and privacy. In summary, `SplitHappens` model outperforms AriaNN in terms of training time and communication, though with an accuracy trade-off.

A major limitation of AriaNN and MSnH is that, at the end of the protocol, both servers must communicate to get the final prediction, potentially revealing client data privacy and make it vulnerable to different attacks. In contrast, `SplitHappens` prevents the output from being disclosed to \mathcal{ADV} and makes it robust to the attacks mentioned above. In conclusion, `SplitHappens` offers a promising alternative to existing protocols by achieving a trade-off between efficiency and privacy. The ability to reduce training time and communication cost, while maintaining a high level of privacy and accuracy, underscore the potential for practical application in PPML.

VII. CONCLUSION

Our research demonstrates that integrating SL with FSS significantly enhances the performance of FSS-based PPML. Our proposed `SplitHappens` approach effectively addresses privacy concerns and maintains efficiency, with only a small accuracy drop compared to the public U-shaped SL protocol. In addition, `SplitHappens` not only boosts communication efficiency and reduces complexity but also achieves the same level of accuracy compared to existing protocols like AriaNN and MSnH. Furthermore, our proposed approach expands the security of MSnH against various attacks like LIA and MIA.

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